

Lawsuit to Stop New Works

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Abstract: Possession is one of the reasons for gaining ownership and one of the ways to prove it, as it plays a distinct role in many countries, as it was not considered about the existing reality and the need to respect it in order to preserve the existing conditions and preserve the stability of transactions only, but it has become a legal necessity and a presumption of ownership if its conditions are met, which are considered by law, as well as it is a presumption of the right until the evidence to the contrary.

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Introduction

Accordingly, there must be legal guarantees to protect the holder of good faith from exceeding others on his possession of the property and we find that the law protects possession for itself and entails its effects regardless of whether it is based or not based on the right recognized by law has developed the Iraqi Civil Law No. (40) of 1951 for possession three lawsuits to protect it is a lawsuit to recover possession and a lawsuit to prevent exposure and a lawsuit to stop new business and this lawsuit protects the possession of real estate only. What interests us in the scope of our research is this lawsuit to stop the new business and we will try in this research to shed light on this lawsuit through the definition and statement of its conditions and elements in terms of litigants or the period required for its establishment or the competent court to consider it.

First: The importance of research

The importance of the research lies in highlighting the legal protection organized by the Iraqi legislator for possession through possession lawsuits, the most important of which is the lawsuit to stop the new business because the legislator always assumes that the holder is the owner of the right and therefore the protection of possession is considered the protection of the owner of the right himself and in this recognition of public order on the one hand and stability of transactions on the other hand.

Second: The research problem

The problem of research arises in the statement of the conditions that must be met to establish a lawsuit to stop the new works so that the holder can establish it before the competent court to consider it, and here the problem of determining the jurisdiction according to whether it is state or spatial.

Third: Research Methodology

The comparative analytical approach was adopted by reviewing the texts of the Iraqi Civil Law, which referred to the lawsuit to stop the new works and comparing them with other laws, in addition to extrapolating some of the competent ruler's rulings issued in this lawsuit.

Fourth: Research Plan

The research will be divided according to a scientific plan consisting of three sections. The first section includes a statement of what a lawsuit to stop the new business and was divided into two requirements. The first of which was devoted to the definition of the lawsuit to stop the new business in jurisprudence and law. The second requirement was devoted to the importance of the lawsuit to stop the new business, either the second section was addressed to the litigants in the lawsuit to stop the new business through two requirements, the first talks about the plaintiff. The second requirement we devoted to determine the defendant in these, The third section was devoted to the statement of the court competent to consider the lawsuit to stop the new business through two requirements, the first of which was devoted to the discussion of state jurisdiction and devoted the second requirement to indicate the spatial jurisdiction and included the search concluded with the most important conclusions and recommendations.

The first topic: the nature of the lawsuit to stop the new works

The legislator has persisted in the protection of possession, not only protected from looting and was not convinced to protect it from exposure, but also organized its protection from exposure before it occurred through a lawsuit to stop new works, and the Iraqi legislator approved this lawsuit in the text of Article (1155) paragraph (1) of the Iraqi Civil Law, which stated (who acquired a property and continued to possess it for a whole year and feared for reasonable reasons exposure to him as a result of new works threatening his possession had to claim in front of Court of First Instance requesting the cessation of these works, provided that they have not been done and that a year has not passed since the start of them).and is characterized by a lawsuit to stop the new business as a preventive lawsuit aimed at protecting the plaintiff and the defendant allows the plaintiff to avoid damage will be caused to him in the future and allow the defendant to avoid the removal of his work and for the purpose of clarifying the concept of this lawsuit will be divided into two requirements, the first of which was devoted to the definition of the lawsuit to stop the new business and the second requirement will address the importance of the lawsuit to stop the new business.

The first requirement: the definition of the lawsuit to stop the new works

The lawsuit to stop the new works is a lawsuit initiated to protect the possession of what is expected to occur on them from the acts of infringement where it is intended to ward off damage to the possession of the property in the future if these works are done, so the subject of this lawsuit is not an exposure has been but works if it was done where there was exposure and damage to the possession of the holder of the property (1). Defined in law.

Subchapter One: Definition of a lawsuit for the cessation of new works in jurisprudence

Through the research, we did not find one of the jurists exposed to this lawsuit in its name, where there is no definition of jurists for this lawsuit, but there are jurisprudential sayings that indicated the legitimacy of this lawsuit, where the jurists do not differ in the legitimacy of this lawsuit, as previous claims of possession, that possession is one of the intended rights of man must be protected by Sharia unless it is found based on a false reason. The blog reads, "I heard an owner and he fought with him in a land where a man had an eye in it, and a man claimed a lawsuit in it, and they fought in it to the owner of those waters, and he stopped them until they went up to the city, and the owner of the eye on which he was came and complained to the owner, and Malik said: It was good when he stopped it and saw that he had been injured, and the owner of the land said: Let

my workers work, and if I deserve the land, let him destroy my work, Malik said: I do not see that, and I see that it stops, if he deserves his right, take it, otherwise it has been proven, I said: Is this without evidence and other than something that stops this land?, Ibn al-Qasim said: I do not see that it stops except that the plaintiff's statement has a face, so the land stops on it. (2). Imam Malik here acknowledged the legitimacy of the lawsuit to stop the new works in the case that was presented to him, the arbitrator owner of that water stopped the plaintiff and the defendant from doing any work in the land in dispute, especially the work of the defendant in digging the well, so he stopped this drilling and prevented it from completing it until this dispute is decided. It will constitute damage to the defendant in his possession, and damage in Islamic jurisprudence is forbidden and removed, and that the origin of preventing damage is modern (no harm and damage) and that the jurists have multiplied their texts on preventing and removing the damage and the defendant's initiation of new works that, if they were done, would have constituted an exposure to the plaintiff's possession, such as apparent damage and a ruling to stop new works such as preventing and cutting damage.

Subchapter Two: Definition of a lawsuit for the cessation of new works in the law

Article (11/3) of the Iraqi Law of Civil Procedure stipulates (a lawsuit to stop the new business, which requires exposure to the holder as a result of new works that have not been threatened to his possession) The Iraqi Civil Law has referred to this lawsuit in the text of Article (1155/1) by saying (whoever acquired a property and continued to possess it for a full year and feared for reasonable reasons exposure to it as a result of new works that threaten his possession, he had to claim before the Court of First Instance requesting the cessation of these works, provided that they are not This is confirmed by the Egyptian Civil Law, especially in Article (962/1) of it (3), and this lawsuit is defined as (the lawsuit filed by the holder of a property or a right in kind on those who embarked on a work if it was to become already exposed to the holder in his possession) and its traditional example is that a person proceeds to dig a foundation in his land to erect a wall and this wall would if it was to block and prevent light and air from building The neighbor, and accordingly the latter files a lawsuit to request the cessation of construction to prevent its completion in order to avoid exposure to it and thus cause him definite damage (4).

There are those who defined it as (the lawsuit filed by the holder against a third party who embarked on a work that if it was done, it would have become exposed to possession by requesting that he be prevented from completing this work) (5)

We can give a simplified definition of a lawsuit to stop the new business, which is as follows (it is the lawsuit filed by the injured (holder) of a possible work carried out by others if this work is done that constitutes a burden on the interest of the holder in his possession of the property).

From this definition, we conclude that for the purpose of enabling the holder to establish this lawsuit, conditions must be available for its establishment, which are the same conditions for filing a lawsuit to prevent exposure, which is that the plaintiff is in possession of the property and that there is actual exposure by others, and that the lawsuit is filed within a year of the occurrence of exposure and that the possession is calm and visible, and that the property can be owned by prescription, and it is worth noting that the judgment issued in this lawsuit is to stop the new business without removing it When the dispute is brought before the Possession Judge, he will issue a judgment that is not free from one of the following two things:

- 1- Either the judge believes that the plaintiff is right in his claim and estimates that there are reasonable grounds with which he fears that there will be actual exposure to the plaintiff's possession if the works to be stopped are completed, and thus the possession judge rules to stop the new works and not to continue them until the right lawsuit or property lawsuit is filed and it is decided after that.

- 2- Or the judge believes that the plaintiff is not right in his lawsuit and he may reject his lawsuit because the conditions of the lawsuit to stop the new works are not available, so he decides to reject the lawsuit and then the defendant continues in the new business that he started until the right lawsuit or property lawsuit is filed (6)

The second requirement: the importance of the lawsuit to stop the new works

The lawsuit to stop the new works is of great importance bestowed by the Iraqi Civil Law, it is a preventive lawsuit aimed at protecting the plaintiff and the defendant, allowing the plaintiff to avoid damage to him in the future and allowing the defendant to avoid removing his business, so this lawsuit is for the purpose of protecting the existing interest of the holder in warding off exposure before it occurs because it is not logical to deprive the holder of legal protection until his possession is assaulted, as it protects possession from future exposure. When the law decided to protect the holder through this lawsuit, it was intended to achieve important goals, on the one hand related to the security of society and the stability of the system in it, noting that this protection prescribed for the holder is temporary, as those who claim otherwise can resort to legal means to prove his right (7). On the other hand, the possession is often based on a right where the holder is the same owner of the thing or the owner of the right in kind over it, if it is not, the litigant must resort to the judiciary to prove his right to the thing in place of possession of the holder in a lawsuit to stop the new business. (8).

The purpose of this lawsuit is to prevent the completion of the work that has not been and is still in the role of implementation, but the holder is affected by it and considers it a threat to his possession, either the works that have already been done may not be the subject of this lawsuit, but replaced by a lawsuit to prevent exposure when the occurrence of exposure is achieved upon the completion of these works and the holder also may request their removal and the judge may assess the nature of these new works by examining each case separately as he has an assessment of the seriousness of these works on the possession of the plaintiff. The great importance of this action is to protect possession from danger before it occurs, because it is not reasonable to deprive possession of the protection of the law until it is actually attacked.

The second topic: litigants in the lawsuit to stop the new works

In this section, God willing, will be talking about the litigants in the lawsuit to stop the new business, and it is known that the word litigants consist of a plaintiff and a defendant and that the knowledge of the plaintiff and the defendant is the most important thing on which the lawsuits are based, as well as the necessary things that must be known by the judge, especially with regard to what is required by one of the environment or the right and the like, and in the lawsuit to stop the new business it was necessary to appoint the described as the plaintiff and the defendant, and we will try in this Section Identify the plaintiff and the defendant in the lawsuit to stop the new works.

The first requirement: the plaintiff in the lawsuit to stop the new works

The plaintiff in the lawsuit to stop the new works is the holder and the owner of the property for a period of one year prior to the occurrence of the assault (9) and the plaintiff must be in possession of the property legally, and also regularly, two important elements must be available: the material element and the moral element.

The plaintiff's possession in an action for the stay of new works must be flawless, i.e. continuous, public, quiet, unambiguous, and the plaintiff's possession of the possessor must be physically connected with it. It is necessary that the possession of the plaintiff in the action to stop the new works with these descriptions mentioned above at the time of the occurrence of the work which, if completed, would have become an exposure to his possession, which is the reason for the filing of an action for the cessation of new works by the plaintiff. The holder must be original, i.e.

permissible for his own account, and not accidental, i.e. not for the account of others, and if the possession is based on an act of tolerance or a license from the administration that may be revoked at any time, the possession It is not accidental as it is not based on an act of tolerance, or on an act of permissibility that a person comes to as a permissible license. The judgment in this lawsuit is in favor of the plaintiff, the judiciary orders the suspension of work, so it does not exceed that to the ruling to remove the work that has been done, which is a temporary judgment like any judgment in possession lawsuits, and the judge may include his judgment in the lawsuit to stop the new works by obliging the convicted person to provide an appropriate guarantee, to be in the case of a ruling to stop the works to ensure the repair of the damage resulting from this situation. When it is found by a final judgment in the matter that the objection to its continuation was unfounded, and in the case of a judgment on the continuation of the works, it is a guarantee that all or part of them will be removed in order to repair the extent that affects the holder if he obtains a final judgment on the origin of the right in his favor. The plaintiff may file a lawsuit to stop the new works against third parties and in the name of the lessor as he is in his possession, taking into account that the lessee may not institute a lawsuit to stop the new works against the lessor on the basis of the relationship between them governed by the contract .The plaintiff may also be the partner in common, whether the lawsuit is to stop an act signed by the partners, or against third parties, the partner may file a lawsuit against his partners even if he is in possession of a certain part of the common property (10).

Second requirement: the defendant in the lawsuit to stop the new works

For the defendant in the lawsuit to stop the new works is the person who performs the works that, if completed, would constitute an exposure to possession, and therefore some commentators of the law summarize the conditions of the lawsuit to stop the new works of the defendant in two conditions:

- 1- That the work carried out by the defendant has begun but has not been completed, that is, it has not yet reached to be an exposure that actually occurred in the possession of the plaintiff, the above statement, the defendant begins to build, a wall in his property or in the land he possesses, even if he proceeded to build this wall until its completion to its end to block this wall light and air on his neighbor or block overlooking his neighbor, resulting in exposure to the neighbor's possession of the neighboring property Or the view.
- 2- For the defendant, the new business must be in his property and not in the plaintiff's property, because if it starts in the property of the holder, a mere fact that it is considered an exposure to possession creates the right to a claim to prevent exposure.This condition is deduced from the nature of things, because if the works had commenced in the plaintiff's property, the exposure would have been immediate and not in the future, and a lawsuit to prevent exposure would have to be filed and not a lawsuit to stop the new works. Al-Sanhouri mentioned the issue of whether the dissatisfied with these acts is complicit with the defendant in their regard, in this case the third party is a partner of the defendant and it is equal to start works in the property of others, and both of them are considered defendants. (11)

The third topic: the competent court to sue the cessation of new works

The legislator distributes jurisdiction between the courts of different types, degrees and places according to multiple criteria to prevent what is related to public order in favor of the public interest, it is not correct to agree on what is contrary to them, including those related to the interest of individuals, so the legislator organizes them and keeps the door open for stakeholders to agree on what is contrary to them and the rules of jurisdiction differ between state, place and qualitative jurisdiction, and we will try in this section to study the jurisdiction of the state and place for the competent courts to sue the cessation of new business.

First Requirement: State Jurisdiction

Starting with the fact that this lawsuit faces the situation in which one of the persons works on his land or on his property is so that it poses a danger to the possession of the person, the latter files a lawsuit demanding the temporary suspension of the new business until it is decided on the origin of the right of the person who has it to take it, the court competent to consider this lawsuit is the Court of First Instance, which is confirmed by Article (1155/1) of the Iraqi Civil Law by saying (who acquired a property and continued to possess it for a whole year and feared for reasonable reasons exposure to it as a result of New works threaten his possession, he had to sue before the Court of First Instance requesting the cessation of the new works).

As for the Egyptian Civil Law, there was no clear and explicit reference within the provisions of the law to the court chosen to consider the lawsuit to stop the new works, and the matter was limited to the text of Article (962) to the effect that the holder submits his lawsuit to the judge requesting the lifting of works that affect his possession.

The competent court, as stipulated in the Civil Law of Iraq, to consider the lawsuit to stop the new business when there are new works issued by others that would have caused damage to the holder in his possession of the property subject to the dispute is the courts of first instance, and therefore this court has ensured, based on the text of the above article, to carry out all legal actions that limit the illegal actions of others.

Second Requirement: Spatial Jurisdiction

The provisions of the Iraqi Civil Law are clear in determining the court competent to consider the lawsuit to stop the new works, and it is worth noting that it is not permissible in advance to agree on what is contrary to this jurisdiction, but it is noted that in some comparative laws, the lawsuit to stop the new works is subject to the jurisdiction of the court, in whose district the property is in dispute, Article (50) of the Civil and Commercial Procedures Law stipulates that: [In real estate and possession lawsuits, the jurisdiction of the court in whose district the real estate or one of its parts is located shall be if it is located in multiple court circuits. The reason why the Egyptian system makes the territorial jurisdiction of the lawsuit to stop the new works is the court in whose jurisdiction the property is in dispute, and did not give the domicile of the plaintiff and the defendant a consideration in the territorial jurisdiction, because the matter may require the court to inspect this property, and also to prevent the issuance of conflicting judgments and for the proper administration of justice.

That is, the general rule in local jurisdiction is that the jurisdiction of the court in whose district the defendant's domicile is located, or in other words, it is not permissible to agree on what is contrary to local jurisdiction to hear real estate lawsuits (12). In addition, the Egyptian Court of Cassation ruled in one of its decisions that the judge of urgent matters in accordance with Article (45) of the Egyptian Civil and Commercial Procedures Law is competent to rule temporarily without prejudice to the right to urgent matters that are feared by the lapse of time, the basis of its jurisdiction is that the order is required to take an urgent decision and that this decision does not affect the origin of the right (13)

It is clear from all of the above that it is not permissible to violate the legal provisions in the knowledge of the court competent to consider lawsuits for stopping new works in a way that ensures stability in transactions, maintains public order and the interest of society and observes the legal rules in force in this regard.

The Conclusion

After research and study on the subject of the lawsuit to stop the new business as a guarantee for the holder of the infringement of others on his rights arising from the property, we have reached at the

end of the research a number of results and recommendations that we will try to mention according to the following detail:

First: Results

- 1- The lawsuit for the cessation of new works is a preventive action aimed at protecting the plaintiff and the defendant, allowing the plaintiff to avoid damage to him in the future and allowing the defendant to avoid the removal of his business.
- 2- In a lawsuit to stop the new works, the judge's decision shall be to stop the works without removing them.
- 3- The lawyer competent to hear new business cessation lawsuits are the courts of first instance and it is suitable to have jurisdiction over the court in whose district the property or the plaintiff's domicile is located.
- 4- A lawsuit to stop new works can be transformed into a lawsuit to prevent exposure.
- 5- The judge considers the lawsuit for the cessation of new works from an objective point of view and can consider it from an urgent point of view whenever the need arises, that is, if the judge wants to provide greater protection to the holder to achieve justice and stability of transactions.

Second: Recommendations

- 1- The necessity of activating the judiciary and giving the judge a wide space to take his discretion on the subject of possession because it is evidence of ownership.
- 2- The need to spread and embody a culture of respect for others for the principle of possession, especially the holder of good faith
- 3- The necessity of the court competent to sue the suspension of new works is the most relevant and most relevant court with the elements of the incident before the judiciary in order to ensure the achievement of justice and the stability of transactions.

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